

Introduction

As a computational ecologist, I seek to advance our collective understanding of ecosystem change. However, this is easier said than done; ecosystems are extraordinarily complex with changes occur on multiple axes simultaneously, and these dynamics can result from any number of mechanisms operating both individually and in concert. Nevertheless, I believe that this complexity can be distilled and studied through the analysis of empirical data—specifically time series, which capture changes in natural and experimental systems. With datasets becoming both higher quality and more available, I believe it is an opportune time to integrate data-driven approaches (i.e. machine learning) with natural history (i.e. domain knowledge) to further the study of ecological change.

My research involves the development of methods for inferring ecological mechanism from time series data. Because time series record the changes in an observed property, they necessarily contain (some) information about the underlying process. Indeed, mathematical advances in the 1980s (Packard et al. 1980; Takens 1981) showed that a single time series is sufficient for reconstructing a model of that process. This approach is broadly referred to as "Empirical Dynamic Modeling" (EDM) and is a practical way to create phenomenological models when explicit mathematical forms fall short. After all, biological processes do not always obey fundamental laws like in physics or chemistry, and it is difficult to correctly divine, *a priori*, the mathematical form that best describes the mechanisms in any given system.

Although EDM is effective at creating models for short-term forecasting, I am interested in the ability to uncover *mechanistic insights*. For example, in my paper on Fraser River sockeye salmon (Ye et al. 2015a), I used "equation-free" methods to recover the nonlinear relationship between environmental conditions and salmon population dynamics using "equation-free" methods; this confirmed existing hypotheses about the drivers of salmon recruitment, which remained hidden to classical fisheries models.

To identify novel problems at the interface of ecology and data science, I frequently work with collaborators and domain experts. For example, in 2012, we described convergent cross mapping (CCM) as a method for identifying causal relationships among time series (Sugihara et al. 2012). Subsequent methods led to a refinement of the CCM method (Ye et al. 2015b) and a multi-lab project to quantify the time lags associated with global-scale climate feedbacks (Nes et al. 2015). My future plans are to continue this cycle of developing new methods and discovering new domain applications. Below are current and future research questions that exemplify such collaborations.

Identifying and Predicting Abrupt Shifts

Large and rapid changes in ecosystem state can be highly disruptive events with substantial impacts on ecosystems and their services. These shifts can occur for many reasons: endogenous dynamics, key parameters that cross a "tipping point", and/or episodic events ~ species invasions, extreme weather (Ratajczak et al. 2018). While some abrupt shifts are clearly recognizable (e.g. a population crash that triggers a trophic cascade), most ecosystems have multiple interacting components, each of which exhibits variability. Characterizing the different forms of abrupt shifts and distinguishing them from other sources of variability will greatly improve our ability to identify, predict, and manage their impacts.

I am currently exploring how EDM methods can shed light on this problem. Recent developments in EDM enable the quantification of interactions that vary in time (Deyle et al. 2016), which can be extended to compute the interaction matrices for the whole system. Initial work suggests that quantities based on this interaction matrix, such as the largest eigenvalue (Ushio et al. 2018) or the trace (Cenci et al. 2019) are related to system stability. My goal is to test these and other metrics as potential indicators of abrupt shifts and community change.

As an initial test case, I am investigating changes in the desert rodent community at Portal, where EDM metrics can be validated against abrupt shifts previously identified by Christensen et al. (2018). Preliminary results (<https://ha0ye.github.io/portalDS/>) indicate that during community reorganizations, the system does not show large changes in the dominant eigenvalue. Instead, the *direction* of the dominant eigenvector, rather than the magnitude of the associated eigenvalue, appeared to be informative for some events.

Although these results suggest that population time series alone are insufficient for predicting all abrupt shifts, they give hope that different types of events could be classified using a suite of EDM-based metrics. My next step is to expand the analysis to encompass datasets from many ecological communities to investigate the frequency of abrupt shifts and commonalities among events. Ultimately, this knowledge could guide predictions and interventions, by identifying the contexts in which regime shifts are driven by endogenous dynamics (and therefore predictable) and the contexts in which shifts are precipitated by stochastic drivers (and therefore inherently unpredictable).

Quantifying the Predictability of Biodiversity Patterns

Although ecological forecasting is an important aim for both ecosystem conservation and management, there is limited knowledge about which ecological properties are predictable; what the quantifiable limits of predictability are; how predictability changes as a function of spatial, temporal, or taxonomic scale; or how to select the best model. Recent work found that time series complexity (as measured by permutation entropy) was an effective predictor of forecast skill, and could be used to identify whether forecast skill was limited by intrinsic properties of the system or sources of error that could be addressed (Pennekamp et al. 2019). I seek to expand on that initial work by increasing the breadth of time series tested, and including multiple methods of forecasting and potential predictors of forecast skill. The aim is to develop a practical guide for selecting a forecasting method, and to identify potential ways to improve forecasts (e.g. via additional data sources, better observations, etc.)

To unravel these myriad factors, I am leading an analysis team to test different methods for forecasting population time series and quantify how properties, such as time series complexity and life history characteristics, influence forecast skill. To enable and support this research, I am also building computational infrastructure that bundles time series data and metadata with templates for reproducible data analyses. This platform will have impacts far beyond this project, by lowering the barrier for macroecological analyses of time series data. For example, anyone can install the package and run just a few lines of code to access over 80,000 population time series, and get started with a template project with a pre-built workflow: <https://weecology.github.io/MATSS/index.html>. This project can then be readily uploaded and shared, thereby enhancing reproducible research practices in ecology.

Reconstructing Functional Responses from Observations

The major promise of machine learning is to derive unknown relationships from data. However, the dependency on data instead of specified mathematical functions can make such models unreliable when making predictions that lie outside the boundaries of the input data. In short, while machine learning approaches excel at *predictive* and *descriptive* modeling, their usage in *causal* modeling is more tenuous. What is most concerning in ecological applications is whether our ability to provide useful forecasts or prescribe interventions is compromised by novel contexts, such as climate change and other non-analogue conditions.

A solution to this problem is to train models on heterogenous data, so that the context-dependent relationships can be accurately inferred by the model (e.g. how the effect of biodiversity on ecosystem function depends on environmental and other factors). Models will then be capable of extrapolating to unobserved conditions, such as new climate regimes or management interventions. In the context of EDM, this means a hierarchical model of the dynamics, from multiple, structured time series datasets (e.g. similar systems across space or environmental gradient). This would merge the EDM approach of reconstructing dynamics from time series, with the causal intervention learning of Athey & Imbens 2016. Currently, I am working with Steve Munch to write software to implement this capability.

As an initial demonstration, I will model the rodent community dynamics at Portal, using a mixed dataset of observations from control plots (all rodents have access) and kangaroo rat enclosure plots (competitively-dominant kangaroo rats are excluded). A generalized model should predict how the community responds to large changes in kangaroo rat abundances. Luckily, a set of treatment reversals, initiated in 2015 (Ernest et al. 2018) and ongoing, provide the perfect validation data to test how well the model can predict the effects of such an intervention. The capability of a general-purpose data-driven tool in this area will enable better solutions for modeling ecological complexity, and more broadly, context-dependent temporal dynamics across domains.

Summary

Although the focus of my work is on theoretical and methodological developments in ecology, my motivations are to improve our understanding of how, in general, ecosystems change. Moreover, the methods have a wide range of applications to complex dynamical systems, within and outside of biology. As such, I thrive on close collaborations with domain experts to provide both key expertise into specific systems of interest, but also to identify novel problems. In some cases, I have even participated in field work and data collection, to get a better sense of where variability in measurements comes from.

In addition, my work is enhanced by open science practices, including open-access publications, as well as sharing data and code. Doing so has magnified the impacts of my work, by making it easier to establish collaborations that apply EDM approaches to novel questions in new systems, as well as empowering other scientists to build upon my work (various software packages that I have worked on comprise ~20,000 total downloads; Ye et al. 2018, Yenni et al. 2019). I would be thrilled to bring my commitment to collaborative computational ecology and tool development to <institution>.

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